

Smart Parking App: Monetizing Residential Parking in Bangalore for Sustainable Urban Mobility

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Abstract – This research paper presents the development of a smart parking app designed to address the parking challenges in Bengaluru. The app enables residential parking space owners to monetize their unused spaces by registering them on the platform, while drivers can easily locate, navigate to, and pay for available parking spots. Key features include real-time parking availability, route calculation with optimization, and secure payment processing, all integrated within a single, user-friendly interface. The app development follows agile methodology for high degree of compartmentalisation and is designed to handle high volumes of requests in real time, ensuring low latency even during peak traffic hours. Its intuitive design minimizes user input while driving, which allows for a seamless user experience. By offering a scalable and secure solution, the app aims to promote sustainable urban mobility and efficient parking space utilization, contributing to better traffic flow and management in Bengaluru.

Keywords – Smart parking app, Bengaluru, residential parking, real-time availability, route optimization, agile methodology, intuitive design, urban mobility, traffic management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Urbanization in major cities like Bengaluru has led to a surge in vehicular traffic, creating significant challenges in managing limited parking spaces. As the number of vehicles on the road continues to grow, drivers often face frustration when searching for available parking,

especially in densely populated areas. This problem is compounded by a lack of infrastructure that efficiently manages residential parking spaces, leading to wasted time, increased fuel consumption, and unnecessary traffic congestion. To address this issue, we require innovative solutions that use modern technology to optimize parking space utilization and improve urban mobility.

One potential solution to this pressing issue lies in the development of a smart parking app, which allows residential parking spaces to be monetized and shared with the public. This approach not only benefits parking space owners, who can generate income from unused spaces, but also provides drivers with a convenient way to find and secure parking spots. By integrating real-time data on parking availability and offering route optimization features, such an app can significantly reduce the time spent searching for parking, contributing to a smoother traffic flow across the city.

The focus of this research is the development of a Smart Parking app that aims to tackle the inefficiencies in parking management in Bengaluru. The app leverages real-time technology to facilitate seamless transactions between parking space owners and drivers. It also incorporates features like secure payment gateways, optimized navigation, and an intuitive user interface designed to make the parking experience hassle-free. By centralizing these functionalities, the app seeks to create a streamlined system that reduces the stress and delays associated with traditional parking methods.

This research paper will explore the design, implementation, and potential impact of the Smart Parking app in Bengaluru. By offering a scalable solution, the app promises to improve urban mobility, enhance parking space utilization, and alleviate traffic congestion, contributing to the city's long-term sustainability goals.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Samar Alkhurajji presents an Android-based smart parking system integrating IR sensors and Arduino for real-time parking availability updates. The system enables pre-booking, saving users time while parking, particularly on university campuses (2020) [1].

Fuquan Pan, et al. introduces a Wi-Fi-based parking guidance system, integrating neural networks and Kalman filtering to improve location accuracy. The system provides real-time parking space allocation and reverse search, addressing parking issues in crowded areas (2021) [2].

Serhat Küçükdermenci proposes a real-time IoT parking monitoring system using Raspberry Pi, IR sensors, and MQTT protocol. The system automates parking management with real-time updates, offering scalable solutions for urban environments (2024) [3].

R.E. Pariama, et al. introduces the Parking-RR app using IoT and ultrasonic sensors for real-time parking availability in Malioboro. It helps users find parking quickly and offers payment options for pre-booking (2021) [4].

Alica Kalašová, Kristián Culík, Miloš Poliak, Zuzana Otahálová, investigate parking inefficiencies in Žilina, Slovakia, and proposes a smart parking system that utilizes IoT for real-time parking guidance. The system reduces traffic congestion by providing parking availability information, improving sustainability in urban areas (2021) [5].

Adnan Md Tayeb, et al., proposes a decentralized parking space-sharing framework using blockchain for secure and transparent transactions between parking space owners and users. The system enables real-time booking, minimizes traffic congestion, and enhances parking efficiency in urban areas (2024) [6].

Mihnea Mihailescu, explores the development of an app designed to crowdsource reports of illegal parking in Bucharest. It discusses the technical and business challenges of adoption, including user engagement, law enforcement validation, and potential legislative changes (2018) [7].

Rahman, et al., proposes an iOS app-based smart parking system to address the inefficiencies of manual parking in urban areas. The app enables users to find and reserve parking spaces, reducing time spent searching and preventing random parking that causes traffic congestion. Comparative analysis shows the system resolves common parking issues and enhances overall efficiency. (2024) [8]

Yesha Patel, et al., this paper presents a smart parking system utilizing Raspberry Pi and an Android app to facilitate pre-booking and real-time booking of parking spaces. The system aims to reduce traffic congestion by storing user data and providing efficient parking access (2020) [9].

Samit Kumar Ghosh, et al., presents a smart car parking system using LabVIEW and IR sensors for real-time slot allocation. The system reduces the time spent searching for parking by displaying exact slot locations and continuously updating availability on a display board, improving parking efficiency in large areas. (2024) [10]

Unlike conventional smart parking systems that rely on sensors or external hardware, this study proposes a purely web-based application operating through user and admin interactions. It enables residential occupants to list unused parking spaces, expanding availability without additional infrastructure. By eliminating hardware dependency, the system reduces costs and complexity while fostering a community-driven approach to urban parking management.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Requirements Specification

R1. The smart parking application will have different users such as, the user (Driver), the owner providing the parking space), and the administrator.

R2. Only the owner and the administrator will have to register with the system and will be authenticated by the

system with user-id and password. The user can start searching for parking spaces immediately.

R3. The Parking lot owners can register their parking spaces to monetize it by mentioning the following details: Parking lots location, how many parking spots are there, two-wheeler/four-wheeler space, are there cameras present, which hours of the day it is available.

R4. Parking lot owners must be able to monetize their parking spots by setting prices and receiving payments directly through the app.

R5. The app must not allow the reservation of parking spots in advance, enforcing a first-come, first-served system.

R6. The users can search a location and they will be able to view the registered parking spots available in the area along with their details.

R7. The user must be able to calculate the time and distance to the available parking spot. The app should also offer route suggestions, allowing users to choose the best route to their parking spot.

R8. Users must confirm occupying a parking spot via their smartphone's GPS/location signal. The app must automatically verify the driver's position in the parking lot.

R9. The app must provide updates on the parking spots in real-time. The users must be able to view the number of available spots in the registered parking space in real-time.

R11. Users must be able to terminate their parking timer without paying for the entire time: if a user occupies a parking spot and selects, for example: an interval of 4 hours but ends up spending only 1 hour. The driver will pay for 1 hour and not their initial estimation.

R12. Administrators must have a control panel to manage the parking lots, Approve or reject parking lot registrations, monitor parking spot availability, and oversee pricing. The Administrator must also have control over user accounts and monetization settings.

R13. The app must support secure payment processing within the app.

R14. The app must not require user input while the user is driving.

B. Use Case Model

Use cases – Search for Parking Spaces, Book Parking Space, List Parking Space, Update Parking Space Listings, Register, Login, View Bookings, Cancel Booking, Leave Review/Rating, Manage User Accounts, Monitor Transactions.

Figure 1. Use Case Diagram of the Parking Space App

C. Use Case Specifications

1) Use Case: Book Parking Space

Actor(s): App User (Driver)

Description: This use case describes how an App User searches for and books a parking space through the application.

Precondition:

- At least one parking space must be available for booking.

Trigger: The App User wants to secure a parking spot and initiates the search within the app.

Basic Flow:

1. The App User (Driver) opens the app and navigates to the "Search Parking Spaces" option.
2. The system presents a search interface with options to filter by location, availability, and price.
3. The App User inputs their search criteria (e.g., location, time, date) for booking the space.
4. The system returns a list of available parking spaces matching the criteria.
5. The App User selects a parking space from the search results.
6. The system shows detailed information about the selected space, including price, availability, Security, Distance.
7. The App User confirms the booking by selecting a time slot and pressing the "Book" button.
8. The system redirects the user to the payment interface.
9. The App User enters payment details and confirms the payment.
10. Upon successful payment, the system confirms the booking and sends a confirmation to the App User.

Alternate Flows:

- No Available Spaces Flow: If no spaces match the search criteria, the system notifies the App User and suggests modifying the search parameters.
- Payment Failure Flow: If the payment fails, the system notifies the App User and prompts them to retry with different payment details.

Post conditions:

- Successful Booking: The parking space is reserved for the App User, and they receive a booking confirmation.
- Failed Booking: If the booking fails (e.g., due to payment issues), the space remains available, and the user is prompted to try again.

Assumptions:

- The payment system is operational and secure.
- The parking space data is accurate and up-to-date.

Figure 2. Activity Diagram for Booking a Parking Space

2) Use Case: List Parking Spaces

Actor: Parking Space Owner

Description: The Parking Space Owner lists available parking spaces they want to rent out on the app, providing details such as the number of spaces, type (two-wheeler or four-wheeler), and additional features like the presence of security cameras.

Precondition:

- The Parking Space Owner must be authenticated and logged into the app.
- The Parking Space Owner must have a registered account with appropriate permissions to list parking spaces.

D. Architecture Diagram

Postcondition:

- The parking spaces are successfully listed on the app, visible to drivers searching for parking spots.
- The system updates the availability and details of the parking spots in real time.

Main Success Scenario:

1. The Parking Space Owner logs into the app.
2. The Parking Space Owner navigates to the Manage Parking Spaces section.
3. The system displays an option to List New Parking Spaces.
4. The Parking Space Owner selects the List New Parking Spaces option.
5. The system prompts the Parking Space Owner to enter the following details:
6. Number of available spaces (e.g., 5 spaces).
7. Vehicle type (e.g., two-wheeler or four-wheeler).
8. Location of the parking lot (e.g., address, coordinates).
9. Additional features (e.g., availability of security cameras, lighting).
10. The Parking Space Owner submits the details.
11. The system validates the input and confirms successful listing.
12. The new parking spaces are made available for users to view and rent through the app.

Alternative Scenarios:

- Invalid Input: If any required field (e.g., number of spaces) is missing or incorrectly formatted, the system displays an error message, prompting the Parking Space Owner to correct the input before proceeding.

Assumptions:

- The system allows multiple parking space listings for the same owner.
- The system provides clear guidance on listing requirements (e.g., input formats for number of spaces, types of features available).

Figure 3. Architecture Diagram of the Parking Space App

1) RESTful/Mobile Client

The mobile application is the primary interface for both drivers and parking space owners. It communicates with the system by sending HTTP requests to the server, enabling users to search for parking spaces, manage listings, and perform bookings in real-time. The client manages interactions like availability checks and payment processing seamlessly.

2) Web Browser Client

Similar to the mobile app, this web-based interface allows users to access the parking management system via desktop or laptop. It facilitates functionality like managing parking spaces, handling user profiles, and processing transactions, utilizing the same HTTP request-response mechanism.

3) RESTful API

The RESTful API acts as the critical intermediary between the clients and the backend server. It processes incoming HTTP requests, handles the necessary

application logic, and sends back structured responses. It ensures smooth, real-time data exchange, enabling core functionality like availability checks, booking, and payment.

4) Login

This module handles user authentication, validating credentials before granting access to the system. Integrated with the database, it ensures secure logins for parking space owners and drivers, establishing session tokens to maintain user sessions.

5) User Interfaces

These include the various interactive elements visible to users on both mobile and web platforms. The UI components are streamlined for ease of use, facilitating functions such as searching for parking spots, managing parking space listings, viewing real-time availability, and processing payments.

Business Layer

6) Application Logic

The application's core processing unit, where booking management, fee calculation, and availability determination occur. This layer also manages dynamic pricing, updates to parking space statuses, and processes transactions. It continuously interacts with the database to ensure accurate, real-time parking space and booking data.

7) Parking Space Controller

Dedicated to managing parking space operations, this component is responsible for CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) actions on parking listings. It dynamically adjusts availability based on user interactions and booking status, ensuring the system remains up-to-date with real-time user activity.

Database Server

8) Database

The central repository for all app data, including user credentials, parking space listings, bookings, and payment records. It supports real-time queries and updates, ensuring that data related to parking space availability, user transactions, and system operations is stored securely and efficiently accessed as required by the application logic.

This research paper explores the development and impact of a Smart Parking app designed to address Bengaluru's parking challenges. By monetizing residential parking and integrating real-time availability, route optimization, and secure payments, the app offers a seamless solution for both owners and drivers. Findings suggest it can reduce parking search time, improve traffic flow, and enhance urban mobility. Its user-friendly design ensures minimal setup and smooth operation in a busy city. Beyond optimizing parking utilization, the app supports sustainable urban development by reducing vehicle circulation and fuel consumption. Successful deployment could serve as a model for other cities. Future research may explore predictive analytics for parking demand, AI-driven dynamic pricing, and integration with EV charging stations to align with sustainability goals.

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